

HadISDH Data Format

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(Previous: HadISDH_Data_Format_v3: <https://zenodo.org/record/7963175>)

(Previous: HadISDH_Data_Format_v3: <https://zenodo.org/record/7962055>)

(Previous: HadISDH_Data_Format_v2: <https://zenodo.org/record/7357311>)

(Previous: HadISDH_Data_Format: <http://cedadocs.ceda.ac.uk/1477>)

(Previous: HadISDHTable v1: <http://cedadocs.badc.rl.ac.uk/1267/>)

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HadISDH Land, Marine, Blend and Extremes Data Format Description

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1) HadISDH.land tables of netCDF file variable names, descriptions and dimensions

Table 1. Generic Dimensions for HadISDH.land

Dimension Name	Dimensions
time	??? months
month	12 months
characters	10 characters
latitude	36 5° gridboxes
longitude	72 5° gridboxes
bound_pairs	2 elements

Table 2. Generic Variables for HadISDH.land

Variable Name	standard_name	long_name	units	Dimensions	cell_methods	comments
time	time	time	days since 1973-1-1 00:00:00	time		
bounds_time	time	time period boundaries		time, bound_pairs		
month		month of year		month, characters		
climbounds		climatology period boundaries		month, bound_pairs, characters		
latitude	latitude	gridbox centre latitude	degrees_north	latitude		
bounds_lat	latitude	latitude gridbox boundaries		latitude, bound_pairs		
longitude	longitude	gridbox centre longitude	degrees_east	longitude		
bounds_long	longitude	longitude gridbox boundaries		longitude, bound_pairs		
meanstncount		mean number of stations within gridbox	1	latitude, longitude	time: mean (interval: 1 month) area: sum where land (stations within	

					gridbox)	
stncount		actual number of stations within gridbox	1		time: sum (interval: 1 month) area: sum where land (stations within gridbox)	
stdunc		uncorrelated combined 2 sigma uncertainty for gridbox	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	time, latitude, longitude		gridbox mean monthly station uncertainty and gridbox sampling uncertainty combined in quadrature assumed uncorrelated
sampunc		uncorrelated 2 sigma sampling uncertainty for gridbox	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	time, latitude, longitude	area: mean where land (stations within gridbox)	gridbox sampling uncertainty (Jones et al 1997) based on spatio-temporal station presence and intersite correlation assumed uncorrelated
stnunc		uncorrelated 2 sigma station uncertainty for gridbox	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	time, latitude, longitude	time: mean (interval: 1 month) area: mean where land (stations within gridbox combined in quadrature)	gridbox mean monthly measurement, adjustment and climatology uncertainty combined in quadrature for each station and then in quadrature over the gridbox assumed to be uncorrelated
measunc		uncorrelated 2 sigma measurement uncertainty for gridbox	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	time, latitude, longitude	time: mean (interval: 1 month) area: mean where land (stations within gridbox combined in quadrature)	gridbox mean monthly measurement uncertainty for each station combined in quadrature over the gridbox assumed to be uncorrelated
climunc		uncorrelated 2 sigma climatology uncertainty for gridbox	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	time, latitude, longitude	area: mean where land (stations within gridbox combined in quadrature)	gridbox mean monthly climatology uncertainty for each station combined in quadrature over the gridbox assumed to be uncorrelated
adjunc		uncorrelated 2 sigma adjustment uncertainty for gridbox	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	time, latitude, longitude	area: mean where land (stations within gridbox combined in quadrature)	gridbox mean monthly adjustment (applied and missed) uncertainty for each station combined in quadrature over the gridbox assumed to be uncorrelated
rbar		intersite correlation (rbar)	1	latitude, longitude		intersite correlation for each gridbox following Jones et al 1997 (rbar)
sbar2		mean gridbox variance (sbar2)	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	latitude, longitude		mean variance over all stations in gridbox following Jones et al 1997 (sbar2)

Table 3. Generic Global Attributes for HadISDH.land

Global Attribute Name	Description
File_created	YYYY-MM-DD HH:MM:SS
Title	title of product
Institution	list of contributing institutions
History	links to further information (additional references, web pages, blogs, twitter handles)
Licence	licensing statement with link to license and instructions on how to cite the data product
Project	overarching project with web page link
Processing_level	brief summary of processes applied to data from source to product
Source	source input data
Comment	any other notes of interest
References	Key journal article to be cited and read for more information
Creator_name	name of main contact author
Creator_email	email for main contact
Version	vX.Y.Z.YYYYp/f: X = major update, Y = minor update, Z = small bug fix or historical data change, YYYY = last year of record, p/f = provisional (p) or final (f)
doi	issued doi for this version
Conventions	CF version that the netCDF file has been checked against

Table 4. Variables for HadISDH.landq/RH/e/Td/Tw/T/DPD. Units are g/kg, %rh, hPa, deg C, deg C, deg C and deg C respectively.

Variable Name	standard_name	long_name	Dimensions	cell_methods	comments
hussa/ hursa/ vpsa/ tdsa/ twsa/ tasa/ dpdsa	-/-/-/-/-/ air_temperature_anomaly/-	near surface (~2m) specific humidity/ relative humidity/ vapour pressure/ dew point temperature/ wet bulb temperature/ air temperature/ dew point depression anomaly	time, latitude, longitude	time: mean (interval: 1 month comment: anomaly from climatology) area: mean where land (stations within gridbox)	gridbox mean monthly mean climate anomaly from stations
huss/ hurs/ vps/ tds/ tws/ tas/ dpds/	specific_humidity/ relative_humidity/-/ dew point temperature/ wet bulb temperature/ air temperature/ dew point depression /	near surface (~2m) specific humidity/ relative humidity/ vapour pressure/ dew point temperature/ wet bulb temperature/ air temperature/ dew point depression	time, latitude, longitude	time: mean (interval: 1 month) area: mean where land (stations within gridbox)	gridbox mean monthly mean from stations
std		near surface (~2m) specific humidity/ relative	time, latitude, longitude	time: mean (interval: 1 month) area: variance	gridbox standard deviation of monthly mean climate

		<i>humidity/ vapour pressure/ dew point temperature/ wet bulb temperature/ air temperature/ dew point depression standard deviation</i>		where land (stations within gridbox)	anomaly from stations
clm		near surface (~2m) specific <i>humidity/ relative humidity/ vapour pressure/ dew point temperature/ wet bulb temperature/ air temperature/ dew point depression climatology</i>	time, latitude, longitude	time: mean (interval: 1 month comment: over 30 year climatology period) area: mean where land (stations within gridbox)	gridbox mean of 30 yr climatological monthly mean from stations

2) Description of ASCII file format

There is an ASCII format file for each variable containing the gridded values for actual (`_actual`), anomalies (`_anomaly8110`) and 2 sigma combined (station [measurement, climatology and homogeneity adjustment] and gridbox spatio-temporal sampling) uncertainties (`_uncertainty2sig`):

e.g.,

`huss_HadISDH-land_HadOBS_19730101-20141231_v2-0-1-2014p_actual.dat`

`huss_HadISDH-land_HadOBS_19730101-20141231_v2-0-1-2014p_anomaly8110.dat`

`huss_HadISDH-land_HadOBS_19730101-20141231_v2-0-1-2014p_uncertainty2sig.dat`

The ASCII version of the gridded data lists each month in turn (from January 1973 to the most recent December) identified by a single row with a four character integer for the year (YYYY), a space and a three character string for the month name (MMM).

Each month has 72 columns of longitude (-177.5W to 177.5E grid cell centres) and 36 rows of latitude (-87.5S to 87.5N grid cell centres). The longitudes and latitudes are listed at file end.

Missing data are identified by -9999.99.

Units are in g/kg, %rh, hPa or degrees C depending on the variable. See Tables 1 to 4 for variable names and descriptions and other information about the product.

3) HadISDH.marine tables of netCDF file variable names, descriptions and dimensions

Table 5. Generic Dimensions for HadISDH.marine

Dimension Name	Dimensions
time	??? months
month	12 months
characters	10 characters
latitude	36 5° gridboxes

longitude	72 5° gridboxes
bound_pairs	2 elements

Table 6. Generic Variables for HadISDH.marine

Variable Name	standard_name	long_name	units	Dimensions	cell_methods	comments
time	time	time	days since 1973-1-1 00:00:00	time		
bounds_time	time	time period boundaries		time, bound_pairs		
month		month of year		month, characters		
climbounds		climatology period boundaries		month, bound_pairs, characters		
latitude	latitude	gridbox centre latitude	degrees_north	latitude		
bounds_lat	latitude	latitude gridbox boundaries		latitude, bound_pairs		
longitude	longitude	gridbox centre longitude	degrees_east	longitude		
bounds_long	longitude	longitude gridbox boundaries		longitude, bound_pairs		
gridcount		number of 1by1 daily grids within gridbox	1	time, latitude, longitude	time: sum (interval: 1 month) area: sum where 1by1 daily grids within gridbox)	
obscount		number of observations within gridbox	1	time, latitude, longitude	time: sum (interval: 1 month) area: sum where observations within gridbox)	
clmgridcount		number of 1by1 daily grids within gridbox climatology	1	month, latitude, longitude	time: sum (interval: 1 month) area: sum where 1by1 daily grids within gridbox)	
clmobscount		number of observations within gridbox climatology	1	month, latitude, longitude	time: sum (interval: 1 month) area: sum where observations within gridbox)	
clmstdgridcount		number of 1by1 daily grids within gridbox climatological standard deviation	1	month, latitude, longitude	time: sum (interval: 1 month) area: sum where 1by1 daily grids within gridbox)	
clmstdobscount		number of observations within gridbox climatological standard deviation	1	month, latitude, longitude	time: sum (interval: 1 month) area: sum where observations within gridbox)	
abs_hgtadjustment		correlated 2 sigma uncertainty for	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	time, latitude, longitude		gridbox mean monthly ship height bias adjustment uncertainty

		ship height bias adjustments for actual values				combined in quadrature assuming correlation
anoms_hgtadjunc		correlated 2 sigma uncertainty for ship height bias adjustments for anomaly values	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	time, latitude, longitude		gridbox mean monthly ship height bias adjustment uncertainty combined in quadrature assuming correlation
abs_instadjunc		correlated 2 sigma uncertainty for instrument bias adjustments for actual values	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	time, latitude, longitude		gridbox mean monthly instrument bias adjustment uncertainty combined in quadrature assuming correlation
anoms_instadjunc		correlated 2 sigma uncertainty for instrument bias adjustments for anomaly values	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	time, latitude, longitude		gridbox mean monthly instrument bias adjustment uncertainty combined in quadrature assuming correlation
abs_clmunc		correlated 2 sigma uncertainty for climatology for actual values	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	time, latitude, longitude		gridbox mean monthly climatology uncertainty combined in quadrature assuming correlation
anoms_clmunc		correlated 2 sigma uncertainty for climatology for anomaly values	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	time, latitude, longitude		gridbox mean monthly climatology uncertainty combined in quadrature assuming correlation
abs_wholeunc		uncorrelated 2 sigma uncertainty for whole number reporting for actual values	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	time, latitude, longitude		gridbox mean monthly whole number uncertainty combined in quadrature assuming no correlation
anoms_wholeunc		uncorrelated 2 sigma uncertainty for whole number reporting for anomaly values	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	time, latitude, longitude		gridbox mean monthly whole number uncertainty combined in quadrature assuming no correlation
abs_measunc		uncorrelated 2 sigma uncertainty for measurement for actual values	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	time, latitude, longitude		gridbox mean monthly measurement uncertainty combined in quadrature assuming no correlation
anoms_measunc		uncorrelated 2 sigma uncertainty for measurement for anomaly values	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	time, latitude, longitude		gridbox mean monthly measurement uncertainty combined in quadrature assuming no correlation
abs_obsunc		uncorrelated 2 sigma combined	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	time, latitude, longitude		gridbox mean monthly combined observations

		observation uncertainty for actual values				uncertainty combined in quadrature assuming no correlation
anoms_obsunc		uncorrelated 2 sigma combined observations uncertainty for anomaly values	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	time, latitude, longitude		gridbox mean monthly combined observations uncertainty combined in quadrature assuming no correlation
abs_sampunc		uncorrelated 2 sigma sampling uncertainty for gridbox	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	time, latitude, longitude	area: mean where marine (ships within gridbox)	gridbox sampling uncertainty (Jones et al 1997) based on spatio-temporal station presence and intersite correlation assumed uncorrelated
anoms_sampunc		uncorrelated 2 sigma sampling uncertainty for gridbox	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	time, latitude, longitude	area: mean where land (stations within gridbox)	gridbox sampling uncertainty (Jones et al 1997) based on spatio-temporal station presence and intersite correlation assumed uncorrelated
pseudostncount		number of pseudo stations within gridbox	1	time, latitude, longitude		
abs_sbarsq		gridbox mean pseudo-station variance (sbarSQ for sampling uncertainty) for gridbox actual values	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	latitude, longitude		mean variance over all observations in gridbox following Jones et al 1997 (sbarSQ)
anoms_sbarsq		gridbox mean pseudo-station variance (sbarSQ for sampling uncertainty) for gridbox anomaly values	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	latitude, longitude		mean variance over all observations in gridbox following Jones et al 1997 (sbarSQ)
meanpseudostncount		mean number of pseudo stations within gridbox	1	latitude, longitude		
abs_rbar		intersite correlation (rbar) for actual values	1	latitude, longitude		intersite correlation for each gridbox following Jones et al 1997 (rbar)
anoms_rbar		intersite correlation (rbar) for anomaly values	1	latitude, longitude		mean variance over all observations in gridbox following Jones et al 1997 (sbarSQ)
abs_stdunc		uncorrelated combined 2 sigma	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	time, latitude, longitude		gridbox mean monthly observation uncertainty and gridbox sampling

		uncertainty for actual values				uncertainty combined in quadrature assumed uncorrelated
anoms_stdu nc		uncorrelated combined 2 sigma uncertainty for anomaly values	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	time, latitude, longitude		gridbox mean monthly observation uncertainty and gridbox sampling uncertainty combined in quadrature assumed uncorrelated

Table 7. Generic Global Attributes for HadISDH.marine

Global Attribute Name	Description
File_created	YYYY-MM-DD HH:MM:SS
Title	title of product
Institution	list of contributing institutions
History	links to further information (additional references, web pages, blogs, twitter handles)
Licence	licensing statement with link to license and instructions on how to cite the data product
Project	overarching project with web page link
Processing_level	brief summary of processes applied to data from source to product
Source	source input data
Comment	any other notes of interest
References	Key journal article to be cited and read for more information
Creator_name	name of main contact author
Creator_email	email for main contact
Version	vX.Y.Z.YYYYp/f: X = major update, Y = minor update, Z = small bug fix or historical data change, YYYY = last year of record, p/f = provisional (p) or final (f)
doi	issued doi for this version
Conventions	CF version that the netCDF file has been checked against

Table 8. Variables for HadISDH.marineq/RH/e/Td/Tw/T/DPD. Units are g/kg, %rh, hPa, deg C, deg C and deg C respectively.

Variable Name	standard_name	long_name	Dimensions	cell_methods	comments
hussa/ hursa/ vpsa/ tdsa/ twsa/ tasa/ dpdsa	-/ -/ -/ -/ -/ air_temperature_anomaly/ -	near surface (~10m) specific humidity/ relative humidity/ vapour pressure/ dew point temperature/ wet bulb temperature/ air temperature/ dew point depression anomaly	time, latitude, longitude	time: mean (interval: 1 month) comment: anomaly from climatology) area: mean where marine (ships within gridbox)	gridbox mean monthly mean climate anomaly from ships
huss/ hurs/ vps/ tds/ tws/ tas/ dpds/	specific_humidity/ relative_humidity/ -/ dew point temperature/ wet bulb	near surface (~10m) specific humidity/ relative humidity/ vapour pressure/ dew point temperature/ wet bulb	time, latitude, longitude	time: mean (interval: 1 month) area: mean where marine (ships within gridbox)	gridbox mean monthly mean from ships

	temperature/ air temperature/ dew point depression /	temperature/ air temperature/ dew point depression			
clmstd		near surface (~10m) specific humidity/ relative humidity/ vapour pressure/ dew point temperature/ wet bulb temperature/ air temperature/ dew point depression climatological standard deviations	time, latitude, longitude	area: mean where marine (ships within gridbox) time: standard deviation of monthly means (interval: 1 month comment: over 30 year climatology period)	30 yr standard deviation of gridbox monthly mean
clm		near surface (~10m) specific humidity/ relative humidity/ vapour pressure/ dew point temperature/ wet bulb temperature/ air temperature/ dew point depression climatology	time, latitude, longitude	time: mean (interval: 1 month comment: over 30 year climatology period) area: mean where marine (ships within gridbox)	30 year monthly mean of gridbox mean

4) HadISDH.blend tables of netCDF file variable names, descriptions and dimensions

Table 9. Generic Dimensions for HadISDH.blend

Dimension Name	Dimensions
Time	??? months
Month	12 months
Characters	10 characters
Latitude	36 5° gridboxes
Longitude	72 5° gridboxes
bound_pairs	2 elements

Table 10. Generic Variables for HadISDH.blend

Variable Name	standard_name	long_name	Units	Dimensions	cell_methods	comments
time	time	time	days since 1973-1-1 00:00:00	time		
bounds_time	time	time period boundaries		time, bound_pairs		
month		month of year		month,		

				characters		
climbounds		climatology period boundaries		month, bound_pairs, characters		
latitude	latitude	gridbox centre latitude	degrees_north	latitude		
bounds_lat	latitude	latitude gridbox boundaries		latitude, bound_pairs		
longitude	longitude	gridbox centre longitude	degrees_east	longitude		
bounds_long	longitude	longitude gridbox boundaries		longitude, bound_pairs		
land_meanstncount		mean number of stations within gridbox	1	latitude, longitude	time: mean (interval: 1 month) area: sum (observations within gridbox)	
land_stncount		actual number of stations within gridbox	1		time: sum (interval: 1 month) area: sum (observations within gridbox)	
marine_gridcount		number of 1by1 daily grids within gridbox	1	time, latitude, longitude	time: sum (interval: 1 month) area: sum (1by1 daily grids within gridbox)	
marine_obscount		number of observations within gridbox	1	time, latitude, longitude	time: sum (interval: 1 month) area: sum (observations within gridbox)	
marine_clmgridcount		number of 1by1 daily grids within gridbox climatology	1	month, latitude, longitude	time: sum (interval: 1 month) area: sum (1by1 daily grids within gridbox)	
marine_clmobscount		number of observations within gridbox climatology	1	month, latitude, longitude	time: sum (interval: 1 month) area: sum (observations within gridbox)	
marine_clmsdgridcount		number of 1by1 daily grids within gridbox climatological standard deviation	1	month, latitude, longitude	time: sum (interval: 1 month) area: sum (1by1 daily grids within gridbox)	
marine_clmsdobscount		number of observations within gridbox climatological standard deviation	1	month, latitude, longitude	time: sum (interval: 1 month) area: sum (observations within gridbox)	
abs_obsunc		uncorrelated 2 sigma combined observation uncertainty for actual values	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	time, latitude, longitude		gridbox mean monthly combined observations uncertainty combined in quadrature assuming no correlation
anoms_obsunc		uncorrelated 2 sigma combined	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	time, latitude, longitude		gridbox mean monthly combined observations

		observations uncertainty for anomaly values				uncertainty combined in quadrature assuming no correlation
abs_sampunc		uncorrelated 2 sigma sampling uncertainty for gridbox	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	time, latitude, longitude	area: mean (observations within gridbox)	gridbox sampling uncertainty (Jones et al 1997) based on spatio-temporal station presence and intersite correlation assumed uncorrelated
anoms_sampunc		uncorrelated 2 sigma sampling uncertainty for gridbox	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	time, latitude, longitude	area: mean (observations within gridbox)	gridbox sampling uncertainty (Jones et al 1997) based on spatio-temporal station presence and intersite correlation assumed uncorrelated
marine_pseudostncount		number of pseudo stations within gridbox	1	time, latitude, longitude		
abs_sbarsq		gridbox mean pseudo-station variance (sbarSQ for sampling uncertainty) for gridbox actual values	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	latitude, longitude		mean variance over all observations in gridbox following Jones et al 1997 (sbarSQ)
anoms_sbarsq		gridbox mean pseudo-station variance (sbarSQ for sampling uncertainty) for gridbox anomaly values	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	latitude, longitude		mean variance over all observations in gridbox following Jones et al 1997 (sbarSQ)
marine_meanpseudostncount		number of pseudo stations within gridbox	1	latitude, longitude		
abs_stdunc		uncorrelated combined 2 sigma uncertainty for actual values	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	time, latitude, longitude		gridbox mean monthly observation uncertainty and gridbox sampling uncertainty combined in quadrature assumed uncorrelated
anoms_stdunc		uncorrelated combined 2 sigma uncertainty for anomaly values	g/kg, hPa, deg C, %rh	time, latitude, longitude		gridbox mean monthly observation uncertainty and gridbox sampling uncertainty combined in quadrature assumed uncorrelated

Table 11. Generic Global Attributes for HadISDH.blend

Global Attribute Name	Description
File_created	YYYY-MM-DD HH:MM:SS
Title	title of product

Institution	list of contributing institutions
History	links to further information (additional references, web pages, blogs, twitter handles)
Licence	licensing statement with link to license and instructions on how to cite the data product
Project	overarching project with web page link
Processing_level	brief summary of processes applied to data from source to product
Source	source input data
Comment	any other notes of interest
References	Key journal article to be cited and read for more information
Creator_name	name of main contact author
Creator_email	email for main contact
Version	vX.Y.Z.YYYYp/f: X = major update, Y = minor update, Z = small bug fix or historical data change, YYYY = last year of record, p/f = provisional (p) or final (f)
doi	issued doi for this version
Conventions	CF version that the netCDF file has been checked against

Table 12. Variables for HadISDH.blendq/RH/e/Td/Tw/T/DPD. Units are g/kg, %rh, hPa, deg C, deg C, deg C and deg C respectively.

Variable Name	standard_name	long_name	Dimensions	cell_methods	comments
hussa/ hursa/ vpsa/ tdsa/ twsa/ tasa/ dpdsa	-/-/-/-/-/ air_temperature_anomaly/-	near surface (~2/10m) specific humidity/ relative humidity/ vapour pressure/ dew point temperature/ wet bulb temperature/ air temperature/ dew point depression anomaly	time, latitude, longitude	time: mean (interval: 1 month comment: anomaly from climatology) area: mean (observations within gridbox)	gridbox mean monthly mean climate anomaly
huss/ hurs/ vps/ tds/ tws/ tas/ dpds/	specific_humidity/ relative_humidity/ -/ dew point temperature/ wet bulb temperature/ air temperature/ dew point depression /	near surface (~2/10m) specific humidity/ relative humidity/ vapour pressure/ dew point temperature/ wet bulb temperature/ air temperature/ dew point depression	time, latitude, longitude	time: mean (interval: 1 month) area: mean (observations within gridbox)	gridbox mean monthly mean from ships
clm		near surface (~2/10m) specific humidity/ relative humidity/ vapour pressure/ dew point temperature/ wet	time, latitude, longitude	time: mean (interval: 1 month comment: over 30 year climatology period) area: mean (observations within gridbox)	30 year monthly mean of gridbox mean

		<i>bulb temperature/ air temperature / dew point depression climatology</i>			
marine_cl mstd		near surface (~2/10m) specific humidity/ relative humidity/ vapour pressure/ dew point temperature/ wet bulb temperature/ air temperature/ dew point depression climatological standard deviations	time, latitude, longitude	area: mean where ocean (observations within gridbox) time: standard deviation of monthly means (interval: 1 month comment: over 30 year climatology period)	30 yr standard deviation of gridbox monthly mean
land_std		near surface (~2/10m) specific humidity/ relative humidity/ vapour pressure/ dew point temperature/ wet bulb temperature/ air temperature/ dew point depression standard deviation		time: mean (interval: 1 month) area: variance where land (observations within gridbox)	gridbox standard deviation of monthly mean climate anomaly from observations

5) HadISDH.extremes tables of netCDF file variable names, descriptions and dimensions

Table 13. Generic Dimensions for HadISDH.extremes

Dimension Name	Dimensions
time	??? months
month	12 months
characters	10 characters
latitude	36 5° gridboxes
longitude	72 5° gridboxes
bound_pairs	2 elements

Table 14. Generic Variables for HadISDH.extremes

Variable Name	standard_name	long_name	units	Dimensions	cell_methods	comments
time	time	time	days since 1973-1-1 00:00:00	time		
bounds_time	time	time period boundaries		time, bound_pairs		
month		month of year		month,		

				characters		
climbounds		climatology period boundaries		month, bound_pairs, characters		
latitude	latitude	gridbox centre latitude	degrees_n orth	latitude		
bounds_lat	latitude	latitude gridbox boundaries		latitude, bound_pairs		
longitude	longitude	gridbox centre longitude	degrees_e ast	longitude		
bounds_long	longitude	longitude gridbox boundaries		longitude, bound_pairs		
meanstncount		mean number of stations within gridbox	1	latitude, longitude	time: mean (interval: 1 month) area: sum where land (stations within gridbox)	
stncount		actual number of stations within gridbox	1		time: sum (interval: 1 month) area: sum where land (stations within gridbox)	

Table 15. Generic Global Attributes for HadISDH.extremes

Global Attribute Name	Description
File_created	YYYY-MM-DD HH:MM:SS
Title	title of product
Institution	list of contributing institutions
History	links to further information (additional references, web pages, blogs, twitter handles)
Licence	licensing statement with link to license and instructions on how to cite the data product
Project	overarching project with web page link
Processing_level	brief summary of processes applied to data from source to product
Source	source input data
Comment	any other notes of interest
References	Key journal article to be cited and read for more information
Creator_name	name of main contact author
Creator_email	email for main contact
Version	vX.Y.Z.YYYYp/f: X = major update, Y = minor update, Z = small bug fix or historical data change, YYYY = last year of record, p/f = provisional (p) or final (f)
doi	issued doi for this version
Conventions	CF version that the netCDF file has been checked against

Table 16. Variables for HadISDH.extremes<var> where <var> can be any of TwX/ TwN/ TwXX/ TwX90p/ TwM90p/ TwM10p/ TwN10p/ TwX25/ TwX27/ TwX29/ TwX31/ TwX33/ TwX35/ TX/ TN/ TXX/ TX90p/ TM90p/ TM10p/ TN10p/ TX25/ TX30/ TX35/ TX40/ TX45/ TX50/ TN18. Units are deg C (for TwX, TwN, TwXX, TX, TN and TXX) and %.

Variable Name	standard_name	long_name	Dimensions	cell_methods	comments
twxa/ twna/ twxa/ twx90pa/ twx10pa/ twm90pa/		near surface (~2m) maximum wet-bulb temperature/ minimum wet-bulb temperature/ maximum maximum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of > 90pct maximum wet-bulb	time, latitude, longitude	time: index (interval: 1 month comment: anomaly from climatology)	gridbox mean monthly index climate anomaly

<p>twm10pa/ twm90pa/ twm10pa/ twx25a/ twx27a/ twx29a/ twx31a/ twx33a/ twx35a/ txa/ tna/ txxa/ tx90pa/ tx10pa/ tm90pa/ tm10pa/ tn90pa/ tn10pa/ tx25a/ tx30a/ tx35a/ tx40a/ tx45a/ tx50a/ tn18a/</p>		<p><i>temperature/ percentage of days per month of < 10pct maximum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of > 90pct mean wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of < 10pct mean wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of > 90pct minimum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of < 10pct minimum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 25 °C maximum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 27 °C maximum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 29 °C maximum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 31 °C maximum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 33 °C maximum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 35 °C maximum wet-bulb temperature/ maximum temperature/ minimum temperature/ maximum maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of > 90pct maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of < 10pct maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of > 90pct mean temperature/ percentage of days per month of < 10pct mean temperature/ percentage of days per month of > 90pct minimum temperature/ percentage of days per month of < 10pct minimum temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 25 °C maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 30 °C maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 35 °C maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 40 °C maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 45 °C maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 50 °C maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 18 °C minimum temperature/ anomaly</i></p>		<p>area: mean where land (stations within gridbox)</p>	<p>from stations</p>
<p>twx/ twm/ twxx/ twx90p/ twx10p/ twm90p/ twm10p/</p>		<p>near surface (~2m) maximum wet-bulb temperature/ minimum wet-bulb temperature/ maximum maximum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of > 90pct maximum wet-bulb</p>	<p>time, latitude, longitude</p>	<p>time: index (interval: 1 month) area: mean where land (stations within</p>	<p>gridbox mean monthly index from stations</p>

<p>twn90p/ twn10p/ twx25/ twx27/ twx29/ twx31/ twx33/ twx35/ tx/ tn/ txx/ tx90p/ tx10p/ tm90p/ tm10p/ tn90p/ tn10p/ tx25/ tx30/ tx35/ tx40/ tx45/ tx50/ tn18/</p>		<p>temperature/ percentage of days per month of < 10pct maximum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of > 90pct mean wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of < 10pct mean wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of > 90pct minimum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of < 10pct minimum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 25 °C maximum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 27 °C maximum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 29 °C maximum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 31 °C maximum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 33 °C maximum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 35 °C maximum wet-bulb temperature/ maximum temperature/ minimum temperature/ maximum maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of > 90pct maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of < 10pct maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of > 90pct mean temperature/ percentage of days per month of < 10pct mean temperature/ percentage of days per month of > 90pct minimum temperature/ percentage of days per month of < 10pct minimum temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 25 °C maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 30 °C maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 35 °C maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 40 °C maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 45 °C maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 50 °C maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 18 °C minimum temperature/</p>		<p>gridbox)</p>	
<p>std</p>		<p>near surface (~2m) maximum wet-bulb temperature/ minimum wet-bulb temperature/ maximum maximum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of > 90pct maximum wet-bulb</p>	<p>time, latitude, longitude</p>	<p>time: index (interval: 1 month) area: variance where land (stations</p>	<p>gridbox standard deviation of monthly index climate</p>

		<p>temperature/ percentage of days per month of < 10pct maximum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of > 90pct mean wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of < 10pct mean wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of > 90pct minimum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of < 10pct minimum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 25 °C maximum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 27 °C maximum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 29 °C maximum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 31 °C maximum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 33 °C maximum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 35 °C maximum wet-bulb temperature/ maximum temperature/ minimum temperature/ maximum maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of > 90pct maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of < 10pct maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of > 90pct mean temperature/ percentage of days per month of < 10pct mean temperature/ percentage of days per month of > 90pct minimum temperature/ percentage of days per month of < 10pct minimum temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 25 °C maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 30 °C maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 35 °C maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 40 °C maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 45 °C maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 50 °C maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 18 °C minimum temperature/ standard deviation</p>		within gridbox)	anomaly from stations
clm		<p>near surface (~2m) maximum wet-bulb temperature/ minimum wet-bulb temperature/ maximum maximum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of ></p>	time, latitude, longitude	time: mean (interval: 1 month comment: over 30 year	gridbox mean of 30 yr climatological monthly

		<p>90pct maximum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of < 10pct maximum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of > 90pct mean wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of < 10pct mean wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of > 90pct minimum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of < 10pct minimum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 25 °c maximum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 27 °c maximum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 29 °c maximum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 31 °c maximum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 33 °c maximum wet-bulb temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 35 °c maximum wet-bulb temperature/ maximum temperature/ minimum temperature/ maximum maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of > 90pct maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of < 10pct maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of > 90pct mean temperature/ percentage of days per month of < 10pct mean temperature/ percentage of days per month of > 90pct minimum temperature/ percentage of days per month of < 10pct minimum temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 25 °C maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 30 °C maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 35 °C maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 40 °C maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 45 °C maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 50 °C maximum temperature/ percentage of days per month of ≥ 18 °C minimum temperature/</p> <p>climatology</p>		<p>climatology period) area: mean where land (stations within gridbox)</p>	<p>index from stations</p>
hq1		<p>Homogeneity Quality Score 1: station count in gridbox</p>	<p>time, latitude, longitude</p>		<p>0=good (2+ stations), 1=moderate quality (1</p>

					station only)
hq2		Homogeneity Quality Score 2: inhomogeneity density per station in gridbox	time, latitude, longitude		0=good (0 inhomogeneities), 2=poor quality (1 inhomogeneity per station)
hq3		Homogeneity Quality Score 3: small (0-0.5 deg C) inhomogeneity density per station in gridbox	time, latitude, longitude		0=good (no small inhomogeneities), 1=moderate quality (1 small inhomogeneity per station)
hq4		Homogeneity Quality Score 4: moderate (0.5-1 deg C) inhomogeneity density per station in gridbox	time, latitude, longitude		0=good (no moderate inhomogeneities), 3=poor quality (1 moderate inhomogeneity per station)
hq5		Homogeneity Quality Score 5: large (1-2 deg C) inhomogeneity density per station in gridbox	time, latitude, longitude		0=good (no moderate inhomogeneities), 5=very poor quality (1 large inhomogeneity per station)
hq6		Homogeneity Quality Score 6: very large (>2 deg C) inhomogeneity density per station in gridbox	time, latitude, longitude		0=good (no moderate inhomogeneities), 10=extremely poor quality (1 very large inhomogeneity per station)
hq7		Homogeneity Quality Score 7: mean adjustment magnitude over stations in gridbox	time, latitude, longitude		0=good (no inhomogeneity), 10=extrem

					ely poor quality ($\geq \pm 2$ deg C mean adjustment per station)
hq8		Homogeneity Quality Score 8: mean absolute adjustment magnitude over stations in gridbox	time, latitude, longitude		No score, just for information
hqscore		Homogeneity Quality Flag: sum of hq1 to hq7	time, latitude, longitude		0=excellent quality, ≥ 7 =poor to very poor quality